

RADIATE

REPORT SERIES

R-001

Report series preview

How to write and submit RADIATE reports

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How to write and submit RADIATE Reports

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Radiate Report R001

ABSTRACT

The RADIATE Report series is an internally reviewed publication initially intended as a vehicle for technical reports, status and progress reports and other material that may be useful for members of the RADIATE consortium, but that would probably not be suitable for publication in an international peer reviewed journal. This report, R001, presents the series and provides information for authors and reviewers. Once reviewed and published RADIATE Reports are fully open access and may be disseminated without limit, as long as the Radiate Report along with its DOI is properly referenced. The copy of reference will always be that archived at the Document Online Identifier (DOI) assigned by the Editors to the accepted report.

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Introduction

The implementation of a Report series for RADIATE partners is a deliverable of the EU Infrastructure project (grant number 824096). The initial intention is to provide a vehicle for publishing technical reports, Milestone and Deliverable reports, technical documents relating to facilities offering Transnational Access (TA) and Joint Research Activities (JRA), or any other technical information, such as useful data tables. The model in mind is that of the Harwell Report series [1]. The Report Series is not intended to replace existing international peer reviewed journals, and it is not expected that it will be catalogued in services such as the ISI Web of Knowledge or Scopus. It differs from simple depository archives, such as ArXiv and HAL, in that the submitted works are subject to internal technical peer review, and the subject scope is limited. It may be considered as an archival system with internal peer review.

The Report series is online-only, fully open access and with no publication or subscription costs. The Report Series has a vocation to continue after the end of the RADIATE project, under conditions to be defined.

Suitable Content

Reports may be submitted by any person or group working within the RADIATE project. This extends to TA users who may wish to make public, progress reports on their research benefitting from TA but not yet ready for publication in an international peer reviewed journal. Reports will be published online as soon as they are accepted, with no specialised sections or volume collation.

Since the Report Series is fully open access, it is not suitable for confidential material, or material likely to subsequently be the object of patent applications and no provisions are in place to cater for this.

Manuscripts submitted from outside of the RADIATE project will not be considered for publication at the present time. This policy may be reviewed in the coming two or three years.

Technical reports may comprise specialised notes concerning any aspects of instruments or facilities used or developed within RADIATE – for example development of charged particle detectors, particle beam handling components, numerical control systems, beam-matter interactions, specialised materials and their properties, quality control reports, and so on. There is no length limit, and embedded data tables, extensive figures, technical drawings, electronic schematics or computer source code and flow diagrams may freely be included. Reviewing of such technical reports will focus on the readability and coherence of the report, and will attempt to identify any clearly erroneous statements or conclusions.

Deliverable and Milestone reports will be expected, of course, to provide clear evidence that the Deliverable or Milestone has indeed been achieved or exceeded.

Reports concerning just useful data are also welcome – for example measured stopping or straggling cross sections; nuclear or atomic interaction cross sections;

sputtering yields; ion charge fractions under different ion transmission conditions. It is difficult to publish such data in international journals without a thorough theoretical discussion of the results, even though the data itself may be useful for other researchers even without the theoretical framework. Reviewing of such Reports will mainly ensure that the data has been correctly obtained and uncertainties properly estimated.

Presentation and documentation of computer codes developed within RADIATE, including user manuals, are also welcomed. Full source code may be included. Computer code intercomparisons, recommendations for common data formats, and validation of simulation codes may also be the object of a RADIATE report.

Reports falling outside of the above general guidelines will be considered by the Editor on a case by case basis, with a policy to try to be inclusive rather than exclusive.

Reviewing will aim to ensure that the work is presented logically and clearly, that any conclusions are adequately supported by the presented material, and that errors of fact or of interpretation are not made.

Publication work flow

The workflow is simple. Reports are submitted by email (or via any cloud-based server if the manuscript is too big for the email systems) to the Editor via RadiateReports@ionbeams.eu. If necessary, the Editor chooses one or more reviewers from the RADIATE partners. The Reviewer(s) submit their review to the Editor, who may ask the author to make changes to the submitted report. Depending on the extent of the changes required, the Editor may again consult the Reviewer(s) but this will be an exceptional case. Once the Editor is satisfied that the Report may be published, the Editor obtains a DOI, finalises the front page of the report (which contains the DOI) and uploads the Report in PDF format to the RADIATE SERIES website [2], where it becomes publicly available.

Stylistic and typographic recommendations

Language

Reports are written in English. All Reports require an Abstract and an Introduction. The structure of the reports after these required sections is at the discretion of the authors. Experimental reports may follow the usual scientific article structure with Methods, Results, Discussion and Conclusion sections, however this structure may be inappropriate for certain reports, such as Milestone and Deliverable reports, computer manuals and so on. It is simply recommended to structure the report into logically distinct sections, with a logical progression amongst the sections, in the interest of readability.

File format

The reports should be submitted in Word .doc or .docx format. Ideally the document should be generated by Word itself rather than with another program that can output ‘word-like’ .doc or .docx files. Macros and automated reference add-ons should be avoided, to keep things as simple as possible for final type-setting tweaks and when the files are read on different machines that may or may not have the appropriate add-ons.

Type-setting recommendations

Please use 12 point Arial, single line spacing, single column, fully justified. Choose portrait A4 paper with 2.5cm margins all around. A section numbering scheme may be used (1. Introduction, 2. Methods, 2.1 TEM, 2.2 TDS etc) or, if the depth of the subsections is not great then bold for the top headings and italics for subheadings, possibly indented to indicate a third level if necessary.

Special care should be paid to avoiding orphaned lines (last line of a paragraph on the next page, for example). There are settings in Word to ensure the absence of orphaned lines.

*This is the Figure
Caption*

Figures will require special attention since the settings for how they behave when text is added near them can be quite subtle. Although Figures and their captions may be collected at the end of the document, it is highly desirable for them to be inserted in the text near where they are referred to. This can be quite complicated when trying to keep captions under the figures while the text flows around the “Figure + Caption”. There is a plethora of methods to insert and control figures, however, in the interests of simplicity a simple and quite robust way to handle this is to insert a text box, which will contain both the Figure and its Caption. The text box parameters may then be set to not flow with the text, and for text to flow around the text box. This is how the Figure on this page was inserted.

Units

SI units [3] and their recognised derivatives (e.g. Å) are required. If in specialised cases it appears better to use another system of units (such as cgs or atomic units) then please address this in the Introduction. Should it become necessary, more detailed recommendations may be made on the use of units. A related recommendation is the use of the term “fluence” for the areal density – for example ions/cm² in ion implantation. “Dose”, which is sometimes erroneously used for this quantity is well defined in radiation physics as energy per unit mass.

Uncertainties

Wherever possible, numerical values, especially those measured in the work presented, should be given with an estimate of the uncertainty on the value. In particular metrological cases it may be necessary to explain what the uncertainty estimate represents however in general, a value of $x \pm y$ is understood to mean that the author asserts that the most probable value is x , with a 33% probability that the real value lies outside of the range $x-y$ to $x+y$. This corresponds to the case where the uncertainty is derived from a Gaussian distribution of mean x and standard deviation y .

References

- [1] <https://discovery.nationalarchives.gov.uk/details/r/C1630>
- [2] <https://zenodo.org/communities/radiate/>
<https://www.ionbeamcenters.eu/radiate/report-series/>
- [3] <https://www.bipm.org/en/publications/si-brochure/>